

Understanding Sleep Paralysis and Health Literacy in College Students

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Introduction:

Wracked with frightening hallucinations that leave agonized individuals temporarily paralyzed, those with sleep paralysis often describe being awake in a body that will not move, trapped between consciousness and sleep. Although neurologically understood as a transient sleep disorder, it remains misunderstood among college students. With a prevalence of 20 - 40% and associations with academic stress and misconceptions are common. Thus, analyzing existing literature would facilitate new research to explore overlooked causes and inform the development of educational interventions in the future.

Objectives:

To explore how college students perceive sleep paralysis, identify perceived causes, and assess their health literacy regarding the condition.

Methods:

A literature search using the terms sleep paralysis, students, causes, and experiences/perception in the Web of Science generated 101 preliminary articles. After excluding studies not addressing perceived causes, psychological or experiential aspects of sleep paralysis in college students, 15 most cited articles were selected. These articles were imported into Excel for bibliometric analysis to identify publication trends, dominant research themes, and gaps related to understanding of the causes of sleep paralysis.

Results:

Analysis of the 15 most frequently referenced keywords revealed two primary themes in the literature: physiological/clinical aspects and sociocultural interpretations. The first group included terms like sleep paralysis (19 references), parasomnia (7 references), and REM sleep (3 references). The second included anxiety (6 references), hallucinations (6 references), and cultural beliefs (3 references). Examining the literature's origins reveals that only one senior author published more than three articles. Most studies appeared in journals categorized under Medicine (n = 8), followed by Psychiatry (n = 4), with Clinical Neurology/Neurosciences and Psychology journals each contributing three publications (n = 3).

Discussion:

The scientists explore sleep paralysis through diverse physiological and sociocultural perspectives, emphasizing biomedical and psychological factors such as anxiety and hallucinations. It overlooks cultural beliefs and health literacy, exposing significant gaps. This study's keyword-level analysis and exclusion of grey literature limit its scope. Future research should explore culturally tailored education and student-centered interventions to close these gaps and improve understanding among college populations.

References:

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